

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF THERMOPLASTIC (PES, PBT) CARBON NANOFIBRE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Novel composites have been prepared by melt blending and conformed by injection moulding. Thermal transitions and crystalline/amorphous structure were determined by DSC. The mechanical behaviour was determined by tensile and fracture impact tests. The results revealed an increase in T_g and Young's modulus in PBT composites attributable to the confinement of CNF by crystalline lamellae and brittle behaviour in both thermoplastic composite systems.

Keywords: thermoplastic, carbon nanofibre, mechanical properties, toughness

INTRODUCTION

Short fibres (mainly glass and carbon) have been widely used in the last decades to reinforce thermoplastic resins. The typical high stiffness and strength of the fibres has been commonly combined with the ductility of many thermoplastics to obtain lightweight composite materials with outstanding mechanical properties for engineering applications.

In the last years, the unique characteristics at a nanometric scale of carbon crystal polymorphs such as carbon nanotubes (CNT) and carbon nanofibres (CNF) have provided new challenges to develop novel nanostructured composites by combining them with thermoplastic matrices [1]. The first studies [2] on the mechanical properties of individual carbon nanoparticles showed very high values of Young's modulus in between 600 and 1000GPa (in regard to 200GPa for steel and 70 GPa for aluminium) and ultimate strength around 150-180 GPa. This would lead to obtain composite materials with very interesting mechanical properties at very low reinforcement volumes. Additionally, the thermal and electrical conductivity can be significantly ameliorated by the inclusion of modest fraction volumes of carbon nanoparticles.

However, the mass scale testing of both CNF and CNT processed at industrial scale showed that these promising individual results were not easy to achieve. Firstly it is not so easy to guarantee the purity of the carbon nanostructures when producing them at industrial scale, and a certain density of defects appear.

The three main issues to deal with in order to get a mechanically efficient CNF/CNT polymer composites are: i) Dispersion of the fibres into the matrix, ii) Alignment of the fibres in the main load direction, and iii) Nanoparticle-resin shear stress transfer [1]

As stated, carbon nanoparticles tend to curve and coalesce into bundles [3] during storage and handling prior to processing. If these agglomerates are present in the final matrix-fibre structure the mechanical properties of the resulting nanocomposites will be affected. Thus, it is of great importance to process the nanocomposites in such a way that the nanoparticles are well dispersed and stretched. Application of a certain amount of shear strain during the mixing (e.g. in a screw extruder) transforms the irregular structures into well dispersed individual fibres, along with fibres alignment in the direction of the shear action.

Chemical modification [4] of the nanofibre surface can also be used to improve the polymer/fibre compatibility. Other successful methods to obtain an increased stress transfer between carbon nano-reinforcements and the resin are in situ polymerisation, covalent functionalisation and polymer grafting [5].

In this study the effect of the addition of 2.5 wt.%, 5 wt.%, and 10 wt. % CNF in a amorphous polymer (PES) and in a semicrystalline polymer (PBT) has been analyzed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Raw Materials

In the preparation of the test specimens, commercial PBT (*BASF Ultradur 4500*) [6] and PES (*BASF Ultrason E 3010*) [7] resins have been used as raw materials, as well as commercial nanofibers from GANF [8]. These nanofibres range from 30nm to 300nm in diameter and are more than 30 μm long.

Processing methods

In order to obtain good CNF dispersions inside the thermoplastic matrix, a double extrusion melt blending process has been performed. In a first stage, the thermoplastic pellets have been melt blended with the CNF. Prior to the blending, the pellets have been dried in a vacuum stove for eight hours. In order to allow for a better extruder feeding and CNF-pellets interaction, a dry pre-blend stage has been carried out. Then, this blend has been melt-extruded to obtain a film. In a second phase, this film has been milled into small pellets of about 1 mm and used to feed the extruder for a second melt blend processing that ameliorates the dispersion of the CNFs into the matrix.

The blended compositions were cut into pellets and injection moulded in a Battenfield PLUS 35 machine to shape the test specimens. The resulting specimens of PBT were air cooled in order to allow for the formation of semi-crystalline structures. Notches for Charpy specimens were milled in a laboratory notching machine, after manually grinding the global shape to get the desired Charpy test specimens. Between 20 and 25

specimens were prepared for each of the nanocomposites compositions, with different notch dimensions.

The following equipment was used to manufacture the test specimens: laboratory stoves, a single screw Brabender Plasti-Corder PL2000 extruder, an industrial mill with 1mm and 10mm sieves, a grinding machine and a laboratory notching machine.

Testing methods

The mechanical behaviour of the PBT/CNF and PES/CNF nanocomposite systems has been characterized by tensile tests according to ASTM-D638-84 [9] at 10mm/min. Fracture toughness assessments were also conducted using Charpy impact tests according to the procedure proposed by Williams and Platti [10] and to ASTM D6110-08 [11].

The thermal transitions of the nanocomposites have been studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) at a heating rate of 10 K/min.

RESULTS

Tensile testing

The stress-strain curves of PBT/CNF and PES/CNF composite systems are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively. Table 1 and Table 2 report the mechanical properties obtained. It is not observed any tensile strength improvement with CNF reinforcement in both systems. In addition a clear reduction in ductility is reported for increasing CNF fraction in both composites. The PBT nanocomposites break in a brittle manner before yielding for 2.5 wt.% CNF contents or higher whilst PES shows ductile behaviour for 5 wt.% CNF or lower contents. In regard to the properties of the elastic region the addition of CNF increases the Young's Modulus in semicrystalline PBT composites, however the reinforcing effect in amorphous PES composites was negligible.

Figure 1. Tensile stress-strain curves of PBT/CNF composites.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of PBT/CNF composites

	Unreinforced PBT	PBT + 2.5%wt.CNF	PBT + 5%wt.CNF	PBT + 10%wt.CNF
Young's Modulus	2.7 GPa \pm 0.1	2.8 MPa \pm 0.1	2.9 MPa \pm 0.1	2.9 MPa \pm 0.1
Yield strength	49.4 MPa \pm 1.9	47.24 MPa \pm 4.7	47.6 MPa \pm 5.0	41.0 MPa \pm 4.1
Yield strain	2.9 % \pm 0.3	2.4 % \pm 0.4	2.3 % \pm 0.4	1.8 % \pm 0.5
Ultimate Strength	41.2 MPa \pm 11	46.2 MPa \pm 4.5	46.1 MPa \pm 4.13	41.6 MPa \pm 4.1
Ultimate Strain	9.3 % \pm 8.2	3.0 % \pm 1.2	2.5 % \pm 0.6	1.8 % \pm 0.5

A lack of adhesion at the CNF/matrix interfaces can be inferred from these results for both composite systems. The load cannot be transferred from the matrix to the fibers, hence it is the matrix who acts as resistant phase and there is no contribution from the fibres. In addition, the presence of bundles and agglomerates of nanofibres was evident in the fracture surfaces. Thus, these bundles must have acted as stress raisers inside the matrix becoming the crack initial points. The higher concentration of bundles for higher CNT contents explains the loss of yield and ultimate strength observed in these composites.

The accelerated crack initiation caused by these bundles leads to early failures around them before the whole ductility of the matrix can be developed, hence and the final rupture takes place in a brittle manner. Pure PES has higher ductility than pure PBT, so it can accommodate better around the bundles by local matrix plastic deformation, retarding the crack propagation, and keeping some level of ductile behavior up to 5 wt.% CNF.

Figure 2. Tensile stress-strain curves of PES/CNF composites.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of PES/CNF composites.

	Unreinforced PES	PES + 2.5%wt.CNF	PES + 5%wt.CNF	PES + 10%wt.CNF
Young's Modulus	2.8 GPa \pm 0.1	2.8 GPa \pm 0.1	2.7 GPa \pm 0.1	2.9 GPa \pm 0.1
Yield strength	78.6 MPa \pm 0.9	74.9 MPa \pm 0.4	77.1 MPa \pm 0.5	69.9 MPa \pm 12.1
Yield strain	5.5 % \pm 0.1	5.4 % \pm 0.1	5.2 % \pm 0.1	4.0 % \pm 1.3
Ultimate Strain	38.4 % \pm 19	8.1 % \pm 1.1	6.2 % \pm 0.4	4.0 % \pm 1.4

The increase of Young's modulus observed in PBT composites suggests a possible confinement of the nanofibres inside the lamellar structure inside the spherulites that disturb chain rearrangement to orient along the applied stress. Cebe et al.[12] have studied the effect of chain confinement of CNT inside PET matrix in fiber form and have proposed that the amount of RAF (Rigid Amorphous Fraction) present in the polymer was increased due to the presence of the nanotubes. Though deeper understanding of these processes is required, signs of strong interaction between the nanoparticles and the bounds of the crystalline phase seem to be present in semi-crystalline matrix nanocomposites, which could affect their mechanical response.

Fracture mechanics parameter (G_c) by impact tests

According to the procedure established by Williams and Platti [12], the slope of the impact energy plot against $B \cdot D \cdot \phi$ corresponds to the value of critical strain energy release rate (G_c) of the material. The results obtained from the Charpy impact tests for

both PBT/CNF and PES/CNF composite systems have been graphically represented in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively

Figure 3 PBT/CNF: G_c determination by Charpy impact tests.

Figure 4 PES/CNF: G_c determination by Charpy impact tests.

It can be clearly observed in both plots that the reinforced materials, in both PBT and PES, show lower slopes than the pure polymers. Thus, it can be inferred that the addition of carbon nanofibres have lead to a significant reduction of the fracture

toughness of both materials, and that further reductions are reported as the carbon nanofibre contents rise.

Table 3. PBT/CNF: G_c values by impact tests

	PBT + 0%CNF	PBT + 5%CNF	PBT + 10%CNF
G_c	1.635 kJ/m ²	1.199 kJ/m ²	0.778 kJ/m ²

Table 4. PES/CNF: G_c values by impact tests

	PES + 0%CNF	PES + 5%CNF	PES + 10%CNF
G_c	1.635 kJ/m ²	1.199 kJ/m ²	0.778 kJ/m ²

The G_c results reported in Table 3 and Table 4 for both PBT/CNF and PES/CNF systems are consistent with the loss of ductility of the material already seen in the tensile tests, which was further accompanied with a slight loss of ultimate strength. Hence, the global capacity of the material to absorb energy before cracking is reduced and the impact energy (and critical strain energy release rate G_c) as well.

DSC analysis

Figure 4 shows the characteristic heat flow curves by DSC obtained for PBT/CNF composites. The degree of crystallinity (X_c) has been calculated according to:

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_m^0 \cdot (1 - w_f)}$$

where ΔH_m is the measured melting enthalpy, w_f is the weight fraction of nanofibres, and ΔH_m^0 is the heat of fusion of fully crystalline PBT. The crystallinity of the nanocomposites slightly decreases from 29% for the pure polymer to about 25% in the 10 wt.% CNF composite (see

Table 5). Also, a continuous increase in the glass transition temperature (T_g) is observed with the nanofibre addition in PBT composites.

On the contrary, the addition of the nanofibres on the amorphous matrix of the PES has shown no clear tendency on the variation of T_g , which can be regarded to remain unaffected by the presence of the nanofibres. Both phenomena indicate that an interaction between the nanofibres and the crystalline phase of the polymer is taking place. On the one hand, the carbon nanofibres difficult the arrangement of the crystalline spherulites during the crystallization stage of PBT, causing the decrease of crystallinity suggesting that these CNF act in PBT rather than as a nucleating agent as an

obstacle to the movements of the polymer chains, hence a higher thermal level is required to get to the glass transition point. The lack of incidence of the nanofibres on the glass transition of PES indicates that this kind of interactions are not so strong in the case of having an amorphous matrix.

Figure 4 DSC curves of PBT/CNF composites.

Table 5. Thermal properties of PBT/CNF composites.

	PBT + 0%wt.CNF	PBT + 2.5%wt.CNF	PBT + 5%wt.CNF	PBT + 10%wt.CNF
T_g [°C]	45.6°C	47.2°C	48.2°C	50.4°C
T_m [°C]	225.3°C	227.9°C	226.8°C	228.2
ΔH_m	41.5 J/g	39.6 J/g	36.0 J/g	32.6 J/g
X_c	29.2%	28.6%	26.7%	25.5%

Figure 5 DSC curves of PES/CNF composites

Table 6. Thermal properties of PES/CNF composites

	PES + 0%CNF	PES + 2.5%CNF	PES + 5%CNF	PES + 10%CNF
T _g [°C]	225.04	229.19	223.96	228.20

CONCLUSIONS

Carbon nanofibre composites were prepared: reinforcing a semi-crystalline matrix (PBT) and an amorphous matrix (PES). Melt blending in a single-screw extruder was used and the resulting film was milled and re-introduced in the extruder as small pellets, in order to improve the nanofibre dispersion; this second film was again milled to obtain the pellet form required to feed the injection unit in which the test specimens were then moulded.

The mechanical properties of these nanocomposites were studied by tensile tests. As well the fracture toughness of the material was assessed from results obtained in the impact Charpy tests. It was observed that no major reinforcement was obtained in terms of yield or ultimate strength. On the contrary, the ductility of both pure polymers was lost at nanofibre contents of about 2.5% wt. or 5% wt. Pure PBT and PES yield values of ultimate strain higher than 20%, however the nanocomposites showed brittle failure. Bundles and agglomerates of nanofibres were present in most of the fracture surfaces, which acted as early crack initiation points. However, an improvement in Young's modulus of PBT based nanocomposites was observed.

The reduction of fracture toughness with the nanofibre content seen in the Charpy impact tests agrees with the loss of ductility obtained in the tensile tests. The inability of the nanocomposites to absorb elastic-plastic energy before collapsing leads to a loss of fracture toughness and to more likelihood of brittle failures.

Finally, the DSC analysis showed a tendency of the semi-crystalline matrix to get higher glass transition temperatures and to reduce crystallinity as the nanofibres content increased. It is suggested that the obstacle that the carbon nanofibres impose to the movement of the polymer chain in PBT could cause both these phenomena and the improved Young's modulus, since none of these effects has been seen in the amorphous based nanocomposites. Hence, it should be studied whether the presence of the nanoparticles could cause an increase in the RAF of the polymers in the interphase between the crystalline and the MAF, and whether this increased RAF could explain all the aforementioned issues.

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References

1. M. Shaffer and I.A. Kinloch. *Composites Science and Technology* 64 (2004), 2281-2282.
2. M. Moniruzzaman y K. I. Winey. *Macromolecules* 2006, 39, 5194-5205.
3. E. Hammel, X. Tang, M. Trampert, T. Schmitt, K. Mauthner, A. Eder and P. Pötschke. *Carbon* 42 (2004) 1153-1158.
4. L. Roy-Xu, V. Bhamipadipati, W. Zhong, J. Li, C. M. Lukehart, E. Lara-Curzio, K.C. Liu, M.J. Lance. *Journal of Composite Materials* 2004; 38; 1563.
5. J.N. Coleman, U. Khan, W.J. Blau, Y.K. Gun'ko. *Carbon* 44 (2006) 1624-1652.
6. BASF ULTRADUR 4500 (PBT) technical datasheet.
7. BASF ULTRASON E 3010 (PES) technical datasheet.
8. Grupo Antolin Nanofibres (GANF) technical datasheet.
9. ASTM-D638-84 Tensile Properties of Plastics
10. E. Plati and J.G. Williams. *Polymer Engineering and Science*, June, 1975, Vol.15, No.6.
11. ASTM D6110 - 08 Standard Test Method for Determining the Charpy Impact Resistance of Notched Specimens of Plastics
12. H. Chen, Z. Liu, P. Cebe. *Polymer* 50 (2009). 872-880.